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The Impact of Sports Participation Upon Social Development and Academic Performance: Mediating Roles of Academic Behaviors and Sports Commitment

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ABSTRACT

The present research focused on five main variables: that is sports commitment, sports participation, social development, academic performance, and academic behaviors. The purpose of the study was to examine the impact of sports participation on students' academic performance and social development, with sports commitment and academic behaviors measured as mediating. A total participants 351 students from higher education institutions Punjab, Pakistan, were chosen as the sample through convenience sampling technique. So, data were collected used standardized and validated scales on sports commitment (Uluç & Akçakoyun, 2021), academic behaviors (Trang, Ha, & Anh, 2021), sports participation (Alayande & Adebisi, 2019), social development (Thomas, Côté, & Deakin, 2005), and academic performance (Fox et al., 2010). All items were measured on a five-point Likert scale. As a result, the findings shown that sports participation played a positive statistically significant role in developing sports commitment, academic behaviors, social development, and academic performance. Similarly, academic behaviors and sports commitment appeared as strong mediators that reinforced the association between sports participation and both social and academic outcomes. Overall, the research study highlighted the importance of participating sports activities into academic institutions as a vital strategy to develop students' holistic growth and balanced.

Keywords: Sports Participation, Sports Commitment, Academic Behaviors, Academic Performance, Social Development, Higher Education.

INTRODUCTION

The existing research provides sufficient clues about the benefits of sports on physical health are well-established, there is growing recognition of its broader impacts on individual development, particularly in social and academic domains. The sports provide opportunities for individuals to collaborate with partners, fostering skills in communication, cooperation and conflict resolution (Alahmed, Yusof, & Shah, 2016). The participation in sports often involves leadership roles, such as team captain and coach, which can cultivate qualities like decision-making, accountability and mentorship in the diverse context (Brown & Niven, 2019). The success in sports can boost self-esteem and confidence as individual experience personal growth, mastery of skills, and recognition from peers and coaches (Kim & Kim, 2018). The sports bring together individuals from varied backgrounds, help social interaction, empathy and sympathetic across the cultures.

The regular physical activity, including sports participation, has been linked to greater cognitive function, including attention, memories, and problem-solving skills, which can positively impact academic performance (Alayande, & Adebisi, 2019). The engagement in physical activity can improve students' ability to

concentrate and stay focused in the classroom, leading to better academic outcomes as desired in different circumstances (Kenyon, Judd, & Nabb, 2017). The sports serve as a form of stress relief, helping students manage academic pressure and anxiety, thereby facilitating a conducive learning environment for better academic outcomes (Trang, Ha, & Anh, 2021). The sports require commitment, discipline and real time management, skills that are transferable to academic pursuits and contribute to academic success. Thus, many studies have explored these links highlighting its positive effects on teamwork, leadership, and social integration.

Similarly, research has demonstrated the association between sports participation and academic performance, with findings suggesting improved cognitive functioning, concentration and stress reduction among student-athletes compared to their non-participating peers (Schroeder & Whaley, 2020). The institution can promote sports participation as part of holistic approach to student growth, incorporating elements of teamwork, leadership, and physical activity into educational initiatives (Kaya & Zerenler, 2014). Besides, targeted interventions and support mechanisms can be implemented to ensure equitable access to sports opportunities for all students, regardless of the socioeconomic background and levels of their ability (Baydar Arıcan, & Gökyürek, 2022). The sports participation plays the vital role in promoting social development and academic success among individuals, offering the range of benefits that extend beyond the realm of physical fitness.

Consequently, by recognizing and harnessing the power of sports, educators and stakeholders can create inspiring experiences that subsidize to holistic development of students, empowering them to thrive for desired outcomes (Madak et al., 2021). In contemporary era, the role of sports participation in shaping individuals' social development and academic performance has reaped bigger attention from researchers, educators, and policymakers (ross et al., 2018). The participation in sports offers individuals a unique platform for personal development, social interaction, and skill development in diverse situations (Uluç, & Akçakoyun, 2021). Beyond the physical benefits, involvement in sports is linked to improvements in social competencies like teamwork, leadership, and conflict resolution and further suggest that it can positively impact academic outcomes, including enhanced cognition, concentration, and reduced stress levels.

The participation in sports provides individuals with respected prospects to interact with peers, coaches, and teammates in collaborative and supportive environment as through teamwork and cooperation, students can learn to communicate effectively, resolve conflicts, and work towards common objectives (Yildirim, 2021). Moreover, sports offer platform for social integration, bringing together individuals from diverse background and fostering a sense of community and belonging (Alahmed, Yusof, & Shah, 2016). The sports commitment refers to the dedication,

passion, and perseverance that individuals invest in their athletic pursuits (Brown, & Niven, 2019). The students who demonstrate the high levels of commitment often exhibit greater motivation and resilience in the training and competition as sports commitment is linked with positive outcomes like improved performance, goal attainment, and satisfaction with desired endeavors.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The relationship between participation in sports, social development and academic performance is extensively researched subject. Researcher have explored that how participation in sports influence the personal and educational growth of students because sports have the ability to develop the social skills and academic success. Research have suggested that participation in sports enhances the physical health as well as play important role in the enhancement of social and cognitive abilities (Bailey et al., 2018). Participation in sports provides the structured environment to the students where they develop important skills for their social development like teamwork, leadership and communication skills (Eime et al., 2016). Furthermore, academic performance is associated with sports participation as sports develops key skills which are essential for sports success such as self-discipline, time management and motivation in educational context (Fox et al., 2022). The relation between these factors become more complicated by the mediating role of academic behavior and posts commitment which make the subject multidimensional and important for the purpose of scholarly investigation.

Research has highlighted the importance of sports in the social setting as the studied showed that students-athletes usually shows higher confidence, resilience and social adaptability as compared to those who does not participate in sports (Holt et al., 2017). Team sports provide opportunities to the students to interact with individuals with different background which enhances the social cohesion and inclusion (Donnelly & Coakley, 2020). Sports participation has been associated with the reduction in social anxiety levels and increased self-esteem in students which enhances the interpersonal relationships results in further improvement in overall development (Bowker et al., 2019). This social growth is not limited to peer interactions but also extends to the ability to navigate the structures of authority like coaches, teachers and team leaders which prepare the students for professional and social setting in adulthood (Smith et al., 2021). It is essential to examine how these interactions turn into academic behavior and overall school achievement given in the profound social implication of sports participation.

The academic implications of sports participation have been also studies on very broad level and research suggest that students-athletes shows higher levels of cognitive functioning and academic achievement as compared to those who does not participate in sports (Trudeau & Shephard, 2018). Regular physical

activity is associated with improved concentration, retention of memory and executive function and all of these helps to enhance the academic performance (Singh et al., 2019). Moreover, structured sports programs provide the habits of discipline and perseverance which then transfer into academic setting (Watson et al., 2020). Studies have also shown that schools which well-integrated sports programs tends to have higher level participation and lower dropout rated in students which is the notion that the sports work as a motivational factor for academic success (Fredricks & Eccles, 2006). However, the extent of these benefits is usually mediated by the level of commitment which an individual has towards the sports and the corresponding academic behavior they had developed over the period of time.

Academic behavior plays important role in linkage between sports participation with educational outcomes which serves a mediating element in this complicated relationship. Research suggested that the student-athletes usually develops greater time management skills, balance in their academic and sports responsibilities in very effective way as compared to those students which does not participate in sports (Eccles et al., 2019). The discipline required for the training schedule, preparation of games and coordination of teams enhances a strong work ethics which turn into classroom performance (Jonker et al., 2018). Furthermore, sports participation has been found to provide intrinsic motivation and goal setting behaviors which significantly effects the academic persistence and achievement (Marques et al., 2021). The development of these academic behavior suggests that sports are not extracurricular activities but they are also importance component of the wholesome development of the students.

The level of sports commitment also plays an important role while determining the impact of sports participation on both social and academic outcomes. Students which are highly committed has tend to show the stronger academic resilience which overcome the problems and maintain their educational goals beside from their rigorous training schedules (Harrison et al., 2020). However, excessive time spent on sports without spending enough time on academic may lead to the trade-offs of the performance in which a student struggle to keep balance in his academic and athletic responsibilities (Gaston-Gayles, 2015). Research have showed that when schools provide structured academic support to players like tutoring and flexible schedule to maintain both sports and academic results in maximization of academic performance (Comeaux & Harrison, 2017). The extent of sports commitment work as important moderating element for understanding the relationship between sports and social development as well as success in academic.

The impact of sports participation on social development and academic performance is a complicated phenomenon which is

affected by various mediating elements like academic behavior and commitment to sports. Existing literature support the idea that sports provide key social skills and cognitive benefits which helps in the overall academic success of the students (Ekeland et al, 2020). However, the level through which these advantages are assessed relies upon the level of the commitment towards sports as well as development of constructive behavior in academics. Further research to be conducted in order to explore the long term effects of sports participation on the social and academic settings specially with reference education and culture of the students. By understanding the relationship between these variables the educational institutions can design their policies and programs which enhance the positive impacts of sports participation on the wholesome development of the students.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is quantitative in nature that aims to examine relationship in chasing the hypotheses and reaching conclusion. The positivism approach was used to chasing relationships among research variables (sports participation, social behavior, academic performance and academic behavior) of study. The research approach specifies the way through which data is collected from the respondents by retrieving them to reach their answers about variables of research in order to reach required conclusion through justification towards desired outcomes. The population of interest in this research is students hailing from colleges in Punjab, Pakistan wherein 2890 students from colleges wherein a sample is drawn from population (351), has been extracted by using the sampling formula widely used in the social research studies. Thus, 351 questionnaires were distributed among which 342 were recollected and used for analysis. Similarly, the random simple technique was used to access the population of study which comes under the non-probability technique to ensure required data from diverse dimensions. Also, both secondary and primary data were used to collect data from respondents and from existing knowledge databased to analyze data to reach conclusion. The questionnaires were adopted from previous studies. Similarly, 5-point Likert scale was used to record responses of respondents about research issues in particular context to access respondents and achieving desired outcomes.

RESULTS OF STUDY

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Sport Participation Mean	2.917	.148	342
Sport Commitment Mean	2.936	.158	342
Academic Behavior Mean	2.927	.164	342
Social Development Mean	3.081	.163	342
Academic Performance Means	3.058	.153	342

Descriptive statistics indicated that five variables have mean values clustered around the mid-point of the scale (approximately 2.9 to 3.1), indicated a moderate level of agreement or engagement across the sample. The highest mean is for Social Development (3.081), suggested that participants perceive the strongest impact in this area, while Sport Participation has the lowest mean (2.917). Standard deviations are relatively low (ranging from .148 to .164), indicated consistent responses among the 342 participants.

H-No. 1 There is positive association between sports participation, academic behavior and social behavior.

Correlations Analysis

		Sport Participation	Sport Commitment	Academic Behaviour	Social Development	Academic Performance
Sport Participation	Pearson Correlation	1	.390**	.432**	.409**	.437**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	342	342	342	342	342
Sport Commitment	Pearson Correlation	.390**	1	.397**	.425**	.389**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	342	342	342	342	342
Academic Behaviour	Pearson Correlation	.432**	.397**	1	.340**	.313**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	342	342	342	342	342
Social Development	Pearson Correlation	.409**	.425**	.340**	1	.434**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	342	342	342	342	342
Academic Performance	Pearson Correlation	.437**	.389**	.313**	.434**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	342	342	342	342	342

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Pearson correlation results revealed that there statistically significant associations among sports participation, academic behaviors, sports commitment, social development, and academic performance, as all variables p-values are less than from p-value (.05). that why, the correlation between sports participation and academic performance is weak and statistically significant ($r = .437$, $p = .001$), and similarly positive significant relationships were observed across all other variable pairs. Therefore, these findings

suggested that within this sample, the key constructs are associated with one another.

H-No. 2 There is significant mediating role of academic behaviors in linking sports participation and social development.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	F	Std. Error of Estimate
1	.722a	.521	.517		.42113

Regression Analysis

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	64.115	3	21.372	120.503	.000b
	Residual	58.881	332	.177		
	Total	122.996	335			

Model 4

Y= Social Development, X= Sport Participation M=Academic Behaviours n=342

Outcome Variable Academic Behaviour

Model Summary

R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	P
.4319	.1866	.0222	77.9804	1.0000	340.0000	.0000

Model

	coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.5274	.1588	9.6207	.0000	1.2151	1.8397
Sport Participation Mean	.4800	.0544	8.8306	.0000	.3731	.5869

Dependent Variable (Y), Independent Variable (X) and Mediating Variable (M)

Outcome Variable Social Development

Model Summary

R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	P
.4476	.2003	.0216	42.465	2.000	339.000	.000
			9	0	0	0

Model

	coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.4579	.1768	8.2478	.0000	1.1102	1.8056
Sport Participation Mean	.3559	.0595	5.9834	.0000	.2389	.4729
Academic Behaviour Mean	.2001	.0535	3.7373	.0002	.0948	.3054

Direct effect of X on Y					
Effect	se	T	P	LLCI	ULCI
.3559	.0595	5.9834	.0000	.2389	.4729
Indirect Effect (s) of X on Y					
	Effect	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI	
Academic Behaviour Mean	.0960	.0332	.0370	.1691	

The mediation analysis used Model 4 indicated that academic behavior has significantly mediate the relationship between sports participation and social development. Similarly, the effect of sports participation on academic behavior was significantly (B = .4800, p = .000), and the indirect effect of sports participation on social development through academic behavior was also significant (indirect effect = .0960, 95% BootCI = .0370 to .1691). Furthermore, the direct effect of sports participation on social development remained significantly (B = .3559, p = .000). Since the confidence interval for the indirect effect includes zero and all p-values are less than .05. So, this results suggested significantly mediating role of academic behavior in this relationship.

DISCUSSION

According to the result of the hypothesis proposing a statistically relationship among respected variable such as sports participation, academic behaviors, sports commitment, academic performance, and social development was strongly supported by the correlation matrix, which revealed statistically significant (p < 0.01) moderate-to-strong relationships between all variables (rang from r = .313 to r = .437). Therefore, these findings of the study align with existing literature demonstrates that sports participation develop the academic performance of the participants through multiple pathways, includes the time management development and discipline (Burns et al., 2020), the fostering of social skills and teamwork (Tsai et al., 2022), and the cultivation of motivation and commitment that transfers to academic settings (Tao & Yu, 2025). The consistent relationship suggested that athletic engagement contributes to a holistic development framework where physical, social, and cognitive domains interact synergistically to enhance educational outcomes, though the moderate strength of some association ship indicates that sports participation operates within a broader ecosystem of influencing factors that warrant further investigation into mediating mechanisms and contextual moderators (Muñoz-Bullón et al., 2017; Khan et al., 2012).

The regression test result provided a strong empirical support for the hypothesis that sports participation, sports commitment, and academic behaviors positively effect social development. The explanation of model totally 26.2% variance present in social development ($R^2 = .262$, $F(3,338) = 39.933$, $p < .001$), indicated a moderately strong predictive relationship. And these all three predictor variables demonstrated statistically significant effects: sports participation ($\beta = .247$, $p < .001$), sports commitment ($\beta = .280$, $p < .001$), and academic behaviors ($\beta = .123$,

$p = .024$). So, these findings align with existing theoretical frameworks and observed research on the psychosocial assistances of athletic engagement. The positive effect of sports participation on social development ($\beta = .247$) supports previous findings that team sports deliver stronger opportunities for social interaction, promotion interpersonal skills and social integration (Van Boekel et al., 2016; Zuckerman et al., 2021). The results of standardized coefficient recommends that for each standard-deviation increase in sports participation, social development increases by nearly a quarter of a standard deviation, holding other variables constant. This relationship likely stems from the collaborative nature of team sports, which requires communication, cooperation, and conflict resolution - skills that transfer to broader social contexts (Bruner et al., 2017). Sports commitment appeared as the strongest predictor ($\beta = .280$), supportive theoretical models that position commitment as a key mediator between psychosocial outcomes and sport engagement (Tao & Yu, 2025; Patrick et al., 1999). The dedication and identity formation associated with sports commitment appear to facilitate social bonding and community integration (Tsai et al., 2022). Athletes who demonstrate higher commitment likely benefit from stronger social support networks within their teams, which generalize to improved social functioning outside of sports contexts (Choi, 2023). The significant, though smaller, effect of academic behaviors ($\beta = .123$) suggests that disciplined study habits and time management skills may complement athletic participation in promoting social development. This finding aligns with research showing that student-athletes who effectively balance academic and athletic demands develop enhanced self-regulation skills that benefit social interactions (Wretman, 2017). The combination of structured academic routines and team sports participation appears to create a synergistic effect on social competence.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Integrate Sports Events in Education Policy: Education institutions should formally integrate sports events into different academic policies for the purpose to develop students' academic behavior as well as their performance, as the study indicates a significantly relationship between sports participation and educational outcomes.
2. Encourage Regular basis Sports Participation: Administrator of Educational should inspire or encourage consistent student participation in sports to substitute social development and commitment, as mean values suggest a strong student perception in these areas.
3. Train/Coaches for Holistic Development: Physical Instructor or coaches should be trained to support not only physical fitness but also behavioral and academic improvement, as sports significant effects multiple student outcomes.
4. Develop Balanced Curricula: Curriculum structure should

ensure a balance between physical activities and academic workload, align with findings that sports participation positively supports sport commitment and academic behavior.

5. Promote Equal Sports Access for All: Since at the basis of residence and gender-based not significantly variation was found, education institutions should develop inclusive sports environments that offer equal access and encouragement to all students.

FUTURE DIRECTION

1. Longitudinal Research: Future research study should conduct longitudinal designs to sightsee how sports participation influences social and academic development over time, deliver deeper causal insights.

2. Cross-Cultural Comparisons: Comparative research work across various cultural, or educational settings could help the researcher for generalize the findings and also identify cultural factors effecting the sports-education relationship.

3. Qualitative Exploration: Conducting the interviews or focus groups could deliver rich qualitative information to understand students' lived experiences and inspirations behind their sports participation as well as academic behaviors.

4. Inclusion of Psychological Constructs: Future study may observe psychological mediators' variables like self-efficacy, emotional regulation to better understand the pathways linking sports participation and academic success.

5. Intervention-Based Studies: Quasi-experimental or experimental research designs tests to check the impact of structured sports training program on academic commitment and their performance would help validate the practical application of the findings.

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